

CITY-MOVE

City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health

HORIZON-HLTH-2023-DISEASE-03

TiDieR description of late interventions

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Meaning
CITY-MOVE	City based interventions to stimulate active Movement for health
CONSORT	Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials
GAPPA	Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030
KCCA	Kampala Capital City Authority
NCDs	Non-communicable diseases
NMT	Non-Motorized Transport Corridor
PA	Physical Activity
SPIRIT	Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials
TIDieR	Template for Intervention Description and Replication
WWII	World war II

1. INTRODUCTION

City environments are a key determinant of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) through several intersecting social, cultural and environmental factors. Cities are associated with lower physical activity (PA), unhealthy diets, overweight and obesity. Environmental factors in cities also influence NCDs (cardiovascular disease, chronic respiratory illnesses, diabetes, and cancers).

Transport systems, building and street designs, and land use patterns also impact NCDs through their influence on air quality, PA, blood pressure, and obesity. Cities are thus both a threat to health and a potential enabler of change. Given the untapped potential of cities to promote PA, CITY-MOVE focuses on adapting the GAPPA (1) to the city-level (city-GAPPA).

CITY-MOVE aims to accelerate and support action for PA at the city level in six cities across three continents: Europe (Antwerp, Ljubljana, and Rotterdam), Africa (Kampala) and Latin America (Bogota and Lima), to learn from cities in different phases and in diverse cultural and macro-economic contexts. The project would evaluate selected late-stage interventions and utilise lessons to inform the implementation of early-stage interventions in all selected cities.

Figure 1: Map of participating cities

To support the description of late-stage interventions, CITY-MOVE employed the Template for Intervention Description and Replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide (2). The TIDieR checklist was developed by an international team to improve the reporting of interventions by helping authors to structure their descriptions and by helping reviewers, editors and readers to evaluate and use the information. The TIDieR checklist, an extension of the CONSORT 2010 (2) and SPIRIT 2013 (3) statements, contains 12 items covering different aspects of intervention reporting. Although it focuses on trials, it is applicable to all study designs. Detailed descriptions of interventions are essential to support effective implementation of useful interventions and their replication.

2. LATE-STAGE INTERVENTIONS OF CITIES

In the following sections, we will describe the reported interventions for each city – Ljubljana, Antwerp, Kampala, Bogota, Rotterdam and Lima.

The description includes the intervention name, why it was developed, what was developed (materials and procedures), who provided it, how and when, tailoring of the intervention, any modifications, and how well it was implemented or how well the plan for the intervention was developed.

The checklist was completed per city for late interventions and provide support intervention documentation and serve as a basis for the subsequent tasks.

2.1. WALK ALONG THE WIRE – LJUBLJANA

The Ljubljana Wire Walk is an annual event organised by the City of Ljubljana. It is aimed at all those who value a healthy lifestyle and would like to experience Ljubljana on foot. The organised walk takes place every year on the Thursday, Friday and Saturday before 9 May, when the end of the Second World War is commemorated throughout Europe. This event is linked to the preservation of Ljubljana's historical memory and is a key element of the city's identity. Otherwise, the Path of Remembrance is open all year round and can be used daily by walkers and cyclists. It serves as a recreational route in the city.

In addition to preserving history, the walk promotes an active and healthy lifestyle, socialising and caring for the environment. In recent years there has been an increase in the number of people taking part in the walk for sporting and recreational reasons. Each participant receives a paper leaflet and is stamped and timed at each of the eight checkpoints. The walk takes place between 6am and 5pm, after which the checkpoints close. Participants who complete the route and collect all the stamps will receive a medal. The walk is organised by the City of Ljubljana and paid for by the participants themselves.

The start of the journey is up to each individual, as is the length of the journey. Stamps are collected at checkpoints to add variety to the running experience. This popular event has been successful in encouraging people to adopt an active lifestyle and socialise. It gives people a chance to get to know Ljubljana in a different way and enjoy good company. The Walk Around the Wire has become an important part of the city's identity and a key event for all those committed to a healthy lifestyle while preserving the city's historical heritage.

For those looking for a greater challenge, there is also the "Triplets' Run", which is held in different lengths – 28, 12 and 3 kilometres for children. During the Yugoslav era, the march was compulsory for schoolchildren, students and employees in Ljubljana, but in independent Slovenia it has lost its socio-political significance. Nevertheless, many people still choose to take part, and in some schools, it is even part of the compulsory physical education curriculum. The march, which has a 66-year tradition, takes place every year and has a loyal following, even without advertising.

Figure 2: Walk around the wire – map and participants

1. **Brief Name:** Walk along the Wire around Ljubljana
2. **Why:** Commemorates the end of WWII, promotes an active lifestyle, socialization, and environmental care.
3. **What:** Leaflet for collecting stamps, medals awarded for completion.
4. **Who Provided:** Organized by the Municipality of Ljubljana.
5. **How:** Face-to-face, individual or group participation.
6. **Where:** 35 km route around Ljubljana.
7. **When and How Much:** Annual event, checkpoints open from 6 am to 5 pm.
8. **Tailoring:** Flexible starting points and walk lengths.
9. **Modifications:** Reduced socio-political significance post-Yugoslavia.
10. **How Well:** High participation without advertising.

2.2. TERLOPLEIN HEALTH KIOSK – ANTWERP

The Terloplein Health Kiosk in Antwerp serves as a community health literacy hub, providing accessible health information and resources to socio-economically disadvantaged residents, including children, adults and marginalised groups such as the elderly, migrants and the homeless. The kiosk provides a range of services and educational materials, including printed and digital resources, free fruit and visual aids on health topics. It operates through a community-based approach, providing health education, interactive workshops and outreach activities. Key services include assistance with COVID vaccination appointments, dietician and exercise coach consultations, tobacco cessation counselling and community health screenings. These screenings measure vital health parameters and provide personalised health advice. The kiosk also promotes mental health, dental health and healthy living and engages the community in activities related to these topics.

Founded by a grassroots initiator and supported by local organisations, the Health Kiosk was initially funded by a philanthropic organisation and later by local policy makers and a university research project. The kiosk is staffed by trained health professionals, community health workers and volunteers, including interns from local educational institutions. To integrate into the community, the kiosk works with local organisations, hosts community-building activities, and uses an open, accessible structure in a public square known for high poverty and crime rates. Building trust was crucial, and initial vandalism was overcome by working with respected community members.

The success of the intervention is based on one-to-one interactions, group sessions and community events that emphasise trust and active participation. It adapts to the specific needs of the community, using different communication methods to overcome language barriers and ensure inclusivity. Continuous improvements are made based on community feedback, and future workshops are planned to maintain engagement.

The project has faced challenges in sustaining funding and fully integrating into the community due to initial mistrust and the negative reputation of some local organisations. Despite these hurdles, the Health Kiosk has provided valuable insights into promoting health literacy and well-being in vulnerable communities, highlighting the need for robust planning, community engagement and long-term support.

Figure 3: Health kiosk

1. **Brief Name:** Terloplein Health Kiosk
2. **Why:** Enhances health literacy and promotes healthy lifestyles for socioeconomically vulnerable populations.
3. **What:** Informational materials, digital resources, free fruit, and visual aids like posters and Kamishibai storytelling.
4. **Who Provided:** Grassroots initiator, local organizations, the European SPICES research project.
5. **How:** Community-based with face-to-face interactions, workshops, education sessions, and free screenings. Involvement of healthcare professionals and community health workers.
6. **Where:** Public square in Borgerhout, Antwerp.
7. **When and How Much:** Open Tuesdays 10:00 to 16:00, regular workshops and sessions.
8. **Tailoring:** Adapted to diverse populations' needs, attention to language, culture, and literacy.
9. **Modifications:** Changes based on feedback, like installing benches and improving facilities.
10. **How Well:** Ongoing improvement based on feedback; faced challenges in sustaining funding and gaining community trust.

2.3. SQUARE FULL OF HEALTH – FAILED INTERVENTION – ANTWERP

The Square Full of Health was a pilot project in Antwerp to improve public health and promote healthy lifestyles. It was based on physical activity checks in the neighbourhoods to encourage street activity. The project worked with LOGO and Vlaams Gezond Leven and focused on the themes of exercise and health in the city.

The project methodology involved the temporary redesign of squares or streets to assess public response and guide future permanent changes. This pilot approach allowed cities to assess public acceptance of health-oriented environments and make informed decisions about permanent redesign to promote healthier urban spaces.

In the Paardenmarkt neighbourhood, the project aimed to temporarily redesign the area with the participation of various stakeholders, including municipal departments, health policy actors and community organisations. The transformation included areas dedicated to sport, social contact and greenery. Activities such as sports events, healthy places and healthy eating workshops were held in the square. The improvements were implemented over a period of 2.5 months.

Figure 4: Square full of health

The project involved extensive community involvement through workshops, focus groups and participatory events. Residents and traders provided feedback to inform the design. Despite the positive community response and initial enthusiasm, the project came to an end due to budget constraints and unmet commitments from local authorities. There were many lessons to be learnt about how temporary redevelopment of urban spaces can promote health, and how community participation plays a key role in such projects.

1. **Brief Name:** Square Full of Health/Plein Vol Gezondheid
2. **Why:** Promotes healthy living through temporary redesigns of public spaces.
3. **What:** Informational materials, workshops, and temporary square redesign.
4. **Who Provided:** Municipal departments, health policy entities, community organizations.
5. **How:** Face-to-face meetings, workshops.
6. **Where:** Paardenmarkt, Antwerp.
7. **When and How Much:** Multiple phases over several years.
8. **Tailoring:** Community feedback for adjustments.
9. **Modifications:** Adjustments based on feedback, no permanent redesign achieved.
10. **How Well:** Extensive planning and participation, but no funding for permanent changes.

2.4. THE GREEN CONNECTION - KAMPALA

In early 2013, the Kampala City Capital Authority (KCCA) initiated a project to reclaim and rehabilitate public green spaces in Kampala. This included plans to repurpose the Sheraton Hotel Gardens and reclaim Kamwokya Children's Public Park from private developers. The city aimed to combat climate change by planting trees and promoting good management of the city's natural assets.

The intervention used tree planting to increase green cover, with land for green spaces donated by volunteers or secured by the government. Historical efforts by colonialists and city authorities contributed to the establishment of green spaces in Kampala.

Intervention providers included urban planning departments staffed by officers trained in urban and physical planning, engineering and public health. The intervention targeted the residents of Kampala and was implemented in locations such as the Sheraton Hotel Kampala and Kamwokya.

The historic parks targeted by the intervention were established in the 19th century and were relatively small 'pocket parks'. The intervention was not personalised and no fidelity assessment was carried out.

Changes to the intervention included the leasing of Sheraton Gardens by KCCA, which hindered public access. The Urban Greening Infrastructure Ordinance aimed to regulate green infrastructure, but faced implementation challenges.

Reports highlighted deficiencies in Kampala's green spaces, including a lack of equipment and insufficient areas for children to play. Efforts to reclaim public spaces from private developers were ongoing, indicating a need for improved accessibility and management. Despite the challenges, the project aims to improve Kampala's green infrastructure and climate resilience.

Figure 5: Sheraton Gardens

Sheraton Gardens

1. **Brief Name:** Sheraton Gardens
2. **Why:** Part of a drive to recover and rehabilitate public green spaces, with goals of climate change mitigation and increased green cover for health and income benefits.
3. **What:** Tree seedlings for increasing green cover, land donated by volunteers or secured by government authority.
4. **Who Provided:** City planning departments, officials with expertise in urban and physical planning.
5. **How:** Community-based, land set aside for green spaces.
6. **Where:** Sheraton Hotel Kampala, within the city center.
7. **When and How Much:** Continuous intervention, established in early 19th century.
8. **Tailoring:** Not applicable.
9. **Modifications:** Efforts to reclaim the gardens from Sheraton Hotel lease, introduction of Urban Greening Infrastructure Ordinance (UGIO).
10. **How Well:** Accessibility issues due to leasing, efforts ongoing to recover for public use.

Kamwokya Children's Public Park

1. **Brief Name:** Kamwokya Children's Public Park
2. **Why:** Similar goals as Sheraton Gardens, with added focus on providing recreational space for children.
3. **What:** Tree seedlings, land donated or secured by government.
4. **Who Provided:** City planning departments, officials with urban planning expertise.
5. **How:** Community-based, involving citizen volunteers.
6. **Where:** Kamwokya, a suburb of Kampala.
7. **When and How Much:** Continuous intervention, gazetted in early 19th century.
8. **Tailoring:** Not applicable.
9. **Modifications:** Challenges in recovering park from private developers, implementation of UGIO.
10. **How Well:** Similar challenges as Sheraton Gardens, with additional focus on lack of equipment for children.

2.5. NON-MOTORIZED TRANSPORT (NMT) PILOT CORRIDOR – KAMPALA

The Non-Motorized Transport (NMT) Pilot Corridor in Kampala was implemented to reduce traffic congestion, provide safe infrastructure for pedestrians and cyclists, and improve overall mobility and health. The project aimed to reduce vehicle congestion, boost business, improve safety and promote the health benefits of walking and cycling.

Materials used included clear signage, road signs and physical barriers to restrict motorised traffic. Community engagement included mapping, feedback and design collaboration with stakeholders. The intervention was implemented by the KCCA Engineering Department in partnership with the Ugandan Ministry of Works and Transport and was physically implemented in Kampala's central business district.

The project focused on busy roads around the old and new minibus parks, an area with heavy vehicle and pedestrian traffic. The corridor stretched from Namirembe Road to Luwum Street. The NMT corridor was constructed once, with bicycle and no-bike signs added later for better enforcement.

The intervention was not personalised and compliance was monitored by KCCA officials and the police to ensure proper use and prevent encroachment. Despite these efforts, some vandalism and abuse was reported.

Figure 6: Non-Motorized Transport (NMT) Pilot Corridor – before and after

1. **Brief Name:** Non-Motorized Transport (NMT) Pilot Corridor
2. **Why:** Address traffic and pedestrian congestion, provide safe infrastructure for pedestrians and cyclists, enhance mobility and reduce pollution.
3. **What:** Clearly labelled and marked NMT corridor with road signs.
4. **Who Provided:** Department of Engineering at Kampala Capital City Authority (KCCA) in collaboration with the Uganda Ministry of Works and Transport.
5. **How:** Community engagement and physical construction of NMT.
6. **Where:** Central business district of Kampala, from Namirembe Road to Luwum Street.
7. **When and How Much:** Constructed once.
8. **Tailoring:** Not applicable. The intervention was not personalised.
9. **Modifications:** Installation of bike signs and barriers to prevent motorized transport encroachment.
10. **How Well:** Local enforcement ensures compliance, though issues with vandalism and misuse reported.

2.6. CICLOVÍA (BOGOTÁ, COLOMBIA)

Ciclovía is an urban intervention in Bogotá, Colombia, where the city streets are closed to motor vehicles every Sunday and holiday from 7am to 2pm. This allows pedestrians, cyclists and users of other non-motorised transport to enjoy the streets. The initiative began in 1974 as a protest against the use of cars, air pollution and the lack of parks. Architects Fernando Caro and Jaime Ortiz proposed the concept to the mayor, and the programme was officially launched in 1976.

Initially managed by the Secretary of Transit and Transport, Ciclovía had minimal impact until 1995, when management was transferred to the Institute of Sport and Recreation. This transition brought with it increased funding, expanded coverage and a vision to create the largest temporary park in the world, improving recreational spaces, physical activity, mental health, social inclusion and air quality.

Today, the Ciclovía covers 127 km and attracts around 1.5 million participants every Sunday, including residents from diverse socio-economic backgrounds. The event is inclusive and welcomes everyone, including those with physical disabilities.

The event is managed logistically by the Institute of Sport and Recreation. At 4am each Sunday, staff load lorries with materials and set up barriers and signs along the route. At 7am, the roads are closed and staff provide security, information and first aid. Other local authorities provide health screening and education, and local vendors sell refreshments and bike repair services. At 2pm the roads are reopened and materials are collected.

In some specific locations spaced throughout the Ciclovía, an enhancement (the Recreovia) is added where sports specialists guide with specific workouts and recreation. Ciclovía has developed through regular evaluations by institutions such as the University of Los Andes and the University of El Rosario. These evaluations have led to continuous improvements. Challenges such as funding and community trust have been addressed through strategic partnerships.

Figure 7 Ciclovía – participants and the map

1. **Brief Name:** Ciclovía
2. **Why:** Initially started as a protest against increasing motor vehicle use, now aims to improve quality of life through recreation, physical activity, and social integration.
3. **What:** Closure of 127 km of streets, deployment of barriers, street signs, and informational materials.
4. **Who Provided:** Managed by the Institute for Sports and Recreation, with involvement from various local authorities.
5. **How:** Streets closed to motor vehicles from 7 am to 2 pm every Sunday and holiday, providing a safe space for non-motorized transportation.
6. **Where:** Across Bogotá, covering low, middle, and high-income areas.
7. **When and How Much:** Weekly, continuous since 1974 with expansions.
8. **Tailoring:** Adapted routes and services, such as health screenings and Recreovía (aerobic classes).
9. **Modifications:** Frequent evaluations and enhancements, including nocturnal Ciclovía events.
10. **How Well:** High participation with 1.5 million users weekly, extensive coordination, and support from various government agencies and independent vendors.

2.7. GREEN WALKING ROUTES – ROTTERDAM

Two late interventions, 'De Groene Connectie' and 'De Groene Overschie', aim to improve the public environment, foster community connections and promote well-being through green walking routes in Rotterdam.

"De Groene Connectie links various green initiatives in Delfshaven and invites residents to explore these spaces for better health. GPs prescribe the route, and the interactive map and promotional materials are available online. Community gardening sessions and walking groups are regularly organised.

Similarly, 'De Groene Overschie' in Overschie offers walking and cycling routes, with GPs encouraging participation. The map provides information on route highlights and community activities. Weekly walking and running groups, cycling initiatives and volunteer opportunities for green maintenance are available.

Both interventions involve partnerships with local organisations and communities to engage residents. Leaflets and maps are distributed in health and social care facilities to promote accessibility.

Delfshaven a city district in the West of Rotterdam hosts "De Groene Connectie", which covers different neighbourhoods along the river Meuse. Overschie, a city district in the North of Rotterdam is home to "De Groene Overschie", with routes through both densely and sparsely built-up areas.

While "De Groene Connectie" started in 2016, the "Walking Prescription" initiative started in 2018, in line with national and local prevention programmes. "De Groene Overschiese" launched in May 2023 and provides continuous access for public use.

Figure 8: Map of the De Groene Overschiese and De Groene Connectie

De Groene Connectie

1. **Brief Name:** De Groene Connectie
2. **Why:** Creates an attractive, livable environment, promotes well-being and social connections.
3. **What:** Map of an 8 km walking route with 21 green initiatives, promotional materials online.
4. **Who Provided:** De Groene Connectie foundation, local green initiatives, and GPs.
5. **How:** Community-based approach, individual and group activities, weekly gardening and walking groups.
6. **Where:** Delfshaven, Rotterdam.
7. **When and How Much:** Continuous intervention since 2016, regular group activities.
8. **Tailoring:** Flexible participation, various group activities.
9. **Modifications:** Ongoing adjustments based on community and partner feedback.
10. **How Well:** High engagement through face-to-face and online promotion.

De Groene Overschiese

1. **Brief Name:** De Groene Overschiese
2. **Why:** Similar to De Groene Connectie, aims to improve public health through green spaces.
3. **What:** Map with walking and cycling routes, highlights of the routes, promotional materials.
4. **Who Provided:** Municipality, WMO Radar, urban green planning organizations, and local partners.
5. **How:** Community-based approach, individual and group activities, weekly walking and cycling groups.
6. **Where:** Overschie, Rotterdam.
7. **When and How Much:** Continuous intervention since May 2023, regular group activities.
8. **Tailoring:** Flexible participation, various group activities.
9. **Modifications:** Adjustments based on initial implementation feedback.
10. **How Well:** Active engagement through multiple channels and community events.

2.8. VMT CASE STUDY “ACTIVE SCHOOLCHILDREN” - LIMA

The Legacy project in Villa María del Triunfo (VMT) and metropolitan Lima encourages school children to use its sports facilities for physical education and ensures the sustainability of these facilities after the Pan American Games in 2019.

Legacy aims to meet the demand for quality physical education spaces in Lima and promote community use of its sports facilities. There are no specific teaching materials; communication is direct with school principals. Schools bring their own sports equipment, while Legacy provides the infrastructure.

The programme is guided by regulations that allow the use of sports facilities for community sports and recreation from Tuesday to Sunday, 6am to 6pm. Schools apply through official channels to use these facilities. The Integration and Promotion Unit manages the relationship with the schools, the Operation and Maintenance Unit manages the availability of the facilities and the physical education teachers of the schools run the classes.

The intervention is face-to-face, scheduled weekly and has been running since 2022. The activities take place in the Villa María del Triunfo sports complex, which includes athletic tracks, sports fields and study rooms. In 2022, 21 educational institutions that have developed sporting events held events for 10,210 children and 2 educational institutions that have developed physical education classes held classes for 1,380 children. In 2023, 20 educational institutions that have developed sporting events held events for 18,974 children and 5 educational institutions that have developed physical education classes held classes for 14,340 children. In total, 44,904 children benefited between 2022 and 2023.

Initially, the Legacy team contacted schools through the Local Unit of Educational Management, but now they contact schools directly to achieve better results. In December 2023, the process was updated to meet ISO 9001 standards, which was achieved in April 2024.

The project conducts quarterly reviews and monthly reports on activities. Between 2022 and 2024, 61,638 children benefited. Schools follow the established application process to use the facilities during school hours.

Figure 9: VMT Sports Complex

1. **Brief Name:** Active Schoolchildren
2. **Why:** To encourage the use of Legacy facilities for physical education by schoolchildren, ensuring sustainability of sports facilities post-2019 Pan American Games.
3. **What:** Use of sports infrastructure, schools bring their own sports equipment.
4. **Who Provided:** Legacy Integration and Promotion Unit and Headquarters Operations and Maintenance Unit.

5. **How:** Face-to-face, scheduled use during the week.
6. **Where:** Villa María del Triunfo Sports Complex, Lima.
7. **When and How Much:** Continuous intervention since 2022, with regular school use.
8. **Tailoring:** Adjustments in approach based on effectiveness, now contacting schools directly.
9. **Modifications:** Compliance with ISO 9001 standard in 2023, ongoing adjustments in space use process.
10. **How Well:** Significant reach with over 61,638 children benefiting from the program between 2022 and 2024.

3. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Rationale and Goals

- **Commonalities:** All interventions aim to improve public health, reduce congestion, and promote active lifestyles through improved infrastructure and community engagement.
- **Differences:** Goals range from memorial and solidarity promoting events (Walk along the Wire) to infrastructure improvements (NMT Corridor) and utilization of existing facilities (Active Schoolchildren).

Materials and Procedures

- **Commonalities:** Use of physical materials such as maps, signs, and promotional materials. Community engagement is a key component.
- **Differences:** Some interventions involve temporary changes (Plein Vol Gezondheid), while others focus on permanent infrastructure (Ciclovía, NMT Corridor).

Delivery and Locations

- **Commonalities:** Interventions typically occur in public spaces with high pedestrian traffic.
- **Differences:** Locations vary from central business districts (NMT Corridor) to sports complexes (Active Schoolchildren) and green spaces (Sheraton Gardens). The Health Kiosk is situated in a socioeconomically vulnerable area, making health services easily accessible.

Duration and Frequency

- **Commonalities:** Continuous or regular interventions, often with periodic community events.
- **Differences:** Annual events (Walk along the Wire) versus weekly activities (Ciclovía, The Health Kiosk) and daily activities (Green Walking Routes).

Tailoring and Modifications

- **Commonalities:** Most interventions incorporate some form of community feedback and adaptation.
- **Differences:** Degree of tailoring varies, with some interventions highly adaptable (Health Kiosk, Square Full of Health, Green Walking Routes) and others standardized (NMT Corridor, Ciclovía, Walk along the wire).

Effectiveness and Challenges

- **Commonalities:** High community engagement and reported benefits in terms of health and safety.
- **Differences:** Challenges include securing permanent funding (Plein Vol Gezondheid), addressing vandalism (NMT Corridor), and building initial community trust (Health Kiosk).

Overall, a total of eight interventions were identified across the cities mostly in the GAPPA domain of active people (02), environments (04) and societies (02) as summarised in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Summary of all reported late interventions

Country - City	Intervention	Target group	GAPPA DOMAIN
Slovenia - Ljubljana	Walk around the wire The Walk along the Wire is for everyone, young and old, and in addition to preserving historical memory, it encourages people to lead active and healthy lifestyles, to socialise and to care for their environment. In recent years, this has been reflected in the increasing number of people taking part in the march for sport and recreation.	Everyone from children in kindergarten to elderly	Active societies
Belgium - Antwerp	Terloplein Health Kiosk The Health Kiosk is an accessible source of health information aimed at people in socio-economically vulnerable circumstances. The aim is to reduce health literacy gaps and promote healthy lifestyles.	Socio-economically disadvantaged residents, including children, adults and marginalised groups such as the elderly, migrants and the homeless	Active people
	Square full of health – failed intervention The intervention to transform Paardenmarkt is part of an integrated approach to healthy urban spaces. The experimental changes are designed to gather feedback and guide sustainable improvements in collaboration with the local community.	Residents of selected neighbourhoods	Active environments
Uganda - Kampala	Green Spaces (2 late interventions) Kampala has launched an effort to restore and rehabilitate public green and open spaces in the city. They are trying to tackle climate change by launching a large-scale tree planting project in Kampala and its suburbs.	Residents of Kampala	Active environments
	Non-Motorized Transport Corridor The NMT pilot project was launched in the city to address traffic and pedestrian congestion on this corridor, provide safe infrastructure for pedestrians and cyclists, and increase safe mobility in the centre of Kampala.	For everyone to reduce traffic congestion and to provide safe infrastructure for pedestrians and cyclists	Active environments
Colombia - Bogota	Ciclovia It allows city streets to be closed to motor vehicles on Sundays, but allows pedestrians, cyclists and other non-motorised means of transport to use these streets.	Everyone – especially pedestrians and cyclists	Active societies
The Netherlands - Rotterdam	Green Walking Routes (2 late interventions) The aim of the greenways is to create an attractive and green environment to promote social interaction and well-being. Both initiatives involve GPs prescribing these walking routes to promote physical activity and mental health among residents.	Residents of Rotterdam	Active people
Peru - Lima	VMT Case Study “Active Schoolchildren” To encourage the use of the Legacy facilities to carry out physical education activities by schoolchildren from Villa María del Triunfo (VMT), and metropolitan Lima, public and/or private educational institutions.	Schoolchildren	Active environments

4. CONCLUSION

This document describes all reported late interventions implemented in cities on 3 continents (South America, Europe and Africa). The comparative analysis highlights the diverse approaches and shared goals of health interventions across different cities. The detailed description of interventions will inform the project's planned evaluation of the late-stage interventions across all cities utilising the Reach, Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation, and Maintenance (RE-AIM) [10] and Practical Robust Implementation and Sustainability Model (PRISM) [11] frameworks. The insights from the evaluation will guide the implementation and evaluation of early-stage interventions in the living labs.

The analysis showed various interventions aimed at improving public health, reducing congestion, and promoting active lifestyles share several commonalities, such as the use of physical materials and community engagement. However, they differ in their specific goals, ranging from memorial events to infrastructure improvements and the utilization of existing facilities. While some interventions involve temporary changes, others focus on permanent infrastructure. Typically occurring in public spaces with high pedestrian traffic, these interventions vary in their specific locations, from central business districts to sports complexes and socioeconomically vulnerable areas. The duration and frequency of these activities also differ, with some being annual events and others occurring weekly or daily.

Community feedback and adaptation are integral to most interventions, though the degree of tailoring varies. While community engagement and reported benefits in terms of health and safety are high across the board, challenges such as securing permanent funding, addressing vandalism, and building initial community trust are common.

Previous studies indicate that the physical environment impacts people's physical activity (5-7). The physical environment can act as a barrier, a facilitator, or a contextual influence. The organization of the physical environment in various cities can explain people's physical activity behaviour (8). Despite numerous studies, there is noticeable inconsistency in the findings, compounded by significant methodological issues in the included studies. The evidence in this review does not support the hypothesis that the multi-component community-wide interventions effectively increased physical activity for the population. However, some studies with environmental components did observe an increase in people walking (9). It is necessary to emphasize that these are "long-standing interventions" which, despite their maturity, must continually evolve and adapt to changes in society, the environment, and health. While they serve as a "baseline," they also provide valuable information and inspiration for new interventions.

Overall, these interventions demonstrate that with strategic planning and community involvement, public health initiatives can be effectively tailored to meet the diverse needs of different urban environments. By addressing specific local needs and leveraging community engagement, these interventions have shown varying degrees of success in promoting public health and sustainable urban development.

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6. ANNEXES

6.1 ANNEX 1 – TIDIER CHECKLIST – WALK AROUND THE WIRE

6.2 ANNEX 2 – TIDIER CHECKLIST – HEALTH KIOSK

6.3 ANNEX 3 – TIDIER CHECKLIST – SQUARE FULL OF HEALTH

6.4 ANNEX 4 – TIDIER CHECKLIST - GREEN SPACES

6.5 ANNEX 5 – TIDIER CHECKLIST - NON-MOTORIZED TRANSPORT CORRIDOR

6.6 ANNEX 6 – TIDIER CHECKLIST - CICLOVIA

6.7 ANNEX 7 – TIDIER CHECKLIST - GREEN WALKING ROUTES

6.8 ANNEX 8 – TIDIER CHECKLIST - ACTIVE SCHOOLCHILDREN